

PHILOLOGY

ENGLISH NEOLOGISMS IN XXI CENTURY

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of nominative processes and lexical changes occurring at the present stage of the development of the English language. It is the lexical system of the language, being the most flexible and mobile, that continuously changes along with the development of the language collective, enriching itself with new lexical units and reflecting current social trends. New the words that have appeared in the language in the last few years have become the object of study of this article.

The material was the neologisms included in the Oxford online dictionary, since 2010. Most of the lexical units under consideration were included in the lists of words of the year of the Oxford Dictionary, formed on the basis of statistical data on the frequency of use in a particular year.

A brief review of theoretical approaches to the problem of studying neologisms and the factors influencing their occurrence is accompanied by a comparison of statistical data of linguists of the late twentieth century — the beginning of the XXI century. The paper examines the specifics of popular neologisms of the English language and their actualization in everyday communication of native speakers.

The study included two stages: analytical, which is a lexical analysis of neologisms, and interactive, consisting in a survey of informants. In semantic terms, a number of generalized thematic groups / spheres of functioning are identified. The identification of the degree of actualization of these linguistic units in the speech of native English speakers consisted directly in a survey of informants. The analysis of the survey results and the attitude of native speakers is given to new words. An attempt has been made to understand the causes of the changes taking place and to offer an interpretation of the results of the study.

Keywords: neologism, language development, language changes, spheres of functioning, language picture of the world.

INTRODUCTION

Language, like any living organism, continuously evolves, enriching itself with a variety of linguistic means. The most mobile and flexible is, as you know, the lexical system of the language, which is changing dynamically and constantly along with the development of a particular language collective, reflecting the changes taking place in society and modern trends. This article is devoted to the lexical metamorphoses of the English language that have been taking place in the last few years and the attitude of native speakers themselves to them.

It should be said that the field of neology, which has been attracting the attention of linguists for more than a decade, is now developing as rapidly as the object of its study itself — new words. And if at the end of the twentieth century . Researchers estimated the number of new English words appearing in the range of 12,000 per year [Barnhart 1985], then in 2002, according to some calculations, this figure increased to 10,000 new words and word forms per day [Metcalf 2004]. The number of neologisms that arise in the language every day in our time is already incalculable. Of course, not all of these words are included in a wide range of usage and fall into dictionaries. Nevertheless, lexicographers are trying to fix all the emerging new lexical units, which allows us to draw a more complete picture of the current trends in the development of the language and the society speaking it.

A large number of works and studies have been devoted to the study and analysis of neologisms, which consider new words from different sides and aspects. The very specificity of the studied object is such that the topic does not exhaust itself, and research works

continue to remain relevant, complementing and clarifying the analyzed phenomenon.

INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "NEOLOGISM"

First of all, we will define the concept itself, which we will operate with in this article. So, in the most general sense, neologisms in the vocabulary are considered words or meanings of existing words that have appeared in the language relatively recently. Irina Retz, having studied the possible approaches of researchers to the interpretation of the term "neologism", which vary depending on the research goals, identifies 5 main theoretical approaches: stylistic, denotative, structural, etymological and lexicographic. Within the framework of the stylistic approach, neologism is interpreted as a word whose novelty is marked by its new stylistic use, an example of which can be words that pass from jargon or metalanguage into everyday language (for example, the term downtime 'time when one is not working or active'). Denotative theory considers neologisms as words that arise to name new objects and concepts and thus acquire new denotative meanings, such as smartphone, selfie, e-book. The structural approach defines neologisms as words that have a completely new linguistic and acoustic form and structure, such as: Tolkien's hobbit. With an etymological approach, a neologism is understood as a word already existing in the language that has developed a new meaning: umbrella 1) 'device used as protection against rain'; 2) 'a protecting force or influence'. And finally, proponents of the lexicographic approach to neologism put into this concept, among other things, the non-fixation of a new word in dictionaries, for example, the cinematherapy language unit 'using films as therapeutic tools', which

scored 70,000 citations in the Google search engine, but has not yet been reflected in lexicographic publications [Rets 2016].

Summarizing these approaches, we can conclude that even the novelty factor common to all definitions seems ambiguous and in many ways contradictory, since the researcher must determine for himself whether a particular language unit is new to all members of society or only for a certain part of native speakers, for the language of everyday communication or only for a certain sublanguage, metalanguage, etc.

In this work, neologisms will be understood as words or phrases that are new in their form and meaning at the current time and have a new socio-cultural meaning. In other words, we will classify as neologisms both new words in form and meaning, and units already existing in the nominative fund, the meaning of which has been transformed due to changes in discursive attribution.

DYNAMICS OF WORD-FORMATION MODELS OF NEOLOGISMS

Various factors influence the creation of new language units. So, L. Gilbert identifies three such factors:

- 1) denominative (the need to designate a new object);
- 2) stylistic (the need for expressively colored speech);
- 3) the pressure of the language system (the formation of potentially possible words based on existing models) [Gilbert 1975, quoted by Gatsalov 2005].

By their nature, neologisms in modern English arise on the basis of various principles. Many linguists note the principle of linguistic economy as dominant at the present stage. The increasingly intense rhythm of life and, as a result, the increasingly acute shortage of time leads to a change in the perception of time in the XXI century, which is noted by sociologists [Urri 2012]. It is quite natural that language, as a kind of mirror of socio-cultural life, changes along with society. At the same time, the changes affect the very nature of the language, in particular its word-formation models. The most popular are merges, abbreviations, abbreviations, which allow you to express a thought using a minimum of linguistic means and spending less time. So, there are the words *MOOC* 'long-distance course', *vom* 'vomit', *hurry sickness* 'an urgent and persistent need to feel busy or productive', *sightjogging* 'visiting a foreign city by jogging around it'.

Statistics also confirm this phenomenon. According to V.I. Zabolotkina, in the 60s and 70s affixation prevailed over word composition, yielding to it only in the 80s. At the end of the twentieth century, one of the most productive linguistic ways of forming a new vocabulary in English was word composition (29.5% of the entire corpus of neologisms), affixation (24%) and conversion (3%). In 2014, some researchers put abbreviations (mergers, abbreviations, acronyms) in second place in frequency [Voelikova 2015], while a few years earlier, Canadian researcher Paul Cook in his doctoral dissertation in 2010, analyzing 1186 of the most frequent neologisms, notes that 43% of new words are formed on the principle of blending [Cook 2010: 41]. It should be noted that in 1991 John Algeo, studying the

dynamics of word-formation models of neologisms, claimed that only 5% of new words account for fusion [Algeo 1991].

RESEARCH OF NEOLOGISMS: AREAS OF OPERATION

Dozens of works by domestic and foreign scientists are devoted to word-formation models of neologisms of the English language. Therefore, it makes no sense to dwell on them in detail in this article. The main purpose of the study, as already noted at the beginning, is to determine the specifics of popular neologisms of the English language and to actualize them in everyday communication of average English speakers.

The material was neologisms included in the Oxford online Dictionary since 2010. The total volume of analyzed words and expressions was 77. The words were selected according to the principle, as it seemed at the initial stage of study, of the most frequent use by native speakers. Thus, most of the lexical units under consideration were included in the lists of words of the year of the Oxford Dictionary, which are formed on the basis of statistical data on the frequency of their use in a particular year.

The study included two stages: analytical, consisting of the selection and lexical analysis of neologisms, and interactive, consisting in a survey of informants.

The presentation of the results of the study will begin with a lexical analysis of the new nominative units. The group of words under consideration included 58% of nouns, 25% of verbs, 13% of adjectives and 4% of abbreviations, followed by more compositionally complex, expanded phrases. Thus, structural and partial analysis indicates the dominant number of one-word linguistic units expressed by nouns, which in turn indicates a greater need for native speakers to name newly appeared phenomena or situations. Note that 49% of the words under consideration are formed by merging, which fully confirms the observations given in the theoretical part regarding the principle of language economy in the context of the accelerating rhythm of life in the XXI century.

In semantic terms, 5 generalized thematic groups / spheres of functioning can be distinguished:

— social and everyday life, including the names of various recently emerged phenomena, habits, everyday objects, etc. (39%): *wine o'clock* 'an appropriate time of day for starting to drink wine'; *cidery* 'a place where cider is made'; to *binge-watch* 'to watch multiple episodes of a television programme in rapid succession'; *fandom* 'the state of being a fan of someone or something'; *showrooming* 'the practice of visiting a shop or shops in order to examine a product before buying it online at a lower price'; *omnishambles* 'a situation that has been comprehensively mismanaged'; *sodcasting* 'the practice of playing music through the loudspeaker of a mobile phone while in a public place'; to *mansplain* 'when a man explains something to a woman in a manner regarded as condescending or patronizing';

— computer technologies and social networks (21%): *selfie* 'a self-portrait photograph'; to *rage-quit* 'to angrily abandon an activity that has become frustrating'; AFK (*away from the keyboard*); *second*

screening 'the practice of watching television while simultaneously using a smartphone, tablet computer, laptop, or other screen device'; *webisode* 'an episode of a series distributed as web television'; to *pocket-dial* 'accidental placement of a phone call while a person's mobile phone is in the owner's pocket or handbag';

— socio-economic spherea (12%): *bedroom tax* 'a reduction in the amount of housing benefit if the property has more bedrooms than is necessary for the number of the people in the household'; *Eurogeddon* 'the catastrophic potential financial collapse in the Eurozone'; *squeezed middle* 'the section of society regarded as particularly affected by inflation, wage freezes, and cuts in public spending'; *crowdsourcing* 'the practice whereby an organization enlists a variety of freelancers, paid or unpaid, to work on a specific task or problem';

— socio-political vocabulary (9%): *Brexit* 'potential withdrawal of the UK from the European Union'; *occupy* *an international movement protesting against perceived economic injustice by occupying buildings or public places and staying there for an extended period of time'; *hacktivism* 'the subversive use of computers and computer networks to promote a political

agenda"; *slacktivism* *actions performed via the Internet in support of a political or social cause but regarded as requiring little time or involvement'; *indyref* 'independence referendum held in Scotland';

— anthropocentric characterizing nominations describing people and their needs, mental qualities, views and beliefs, style, etc. (19%): *moblivious* 'staring at your phone whilst walking or driving and oblivious of your surroundings'; *sapiosexual* *a sapiosexual is a person who finds intelligence a sexually attractive quality in others"; *adorkable* "unfashionable or socially awkward in a way regarded as appealing or cute"; *hangry* 'being so hungry that the lack of food causes a person to become angry and frustrated'; *on fleek* 'extremely good, attractive, or stylish'; *normcore* 'a trend in which ordinary, unfashionable clothing is worn as a deliberate fashion statement: *lumbersexual* 'a young urban man who cultivates an appearance and style of dress suggestive of a rugged outdoor lifestyle'.

I recognize the conditionality of this division into groups and the names of the thematic groups themselves (see Fig.). This is caused by a number of reasons, and first of all by the presence of schemes in one word that allow it to be attributed to several areas at once.

Fig. Thematic groups of neologisms

As a percentage, the most productive neologisms in terms of education are the sphere of public and everyday life - 39%, followed by the rapidly developing field of new technologies, the Internet and social networks - 21% and then a rather heterogeneous group, which we have designated as anthropocentric nominations that characterize people and their needs, abilities, manners and style, etc., which occupies 19% of the total number of analyzed words.

INTERACTIVE STUDY OF NEOLOGISMS AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The second part of the study, aimed at identifying the degree of actualization of these linguistic units in the speech of native English speakers, consisted directly in a survey of native-speaking informants living in the UK. During the survey, informants were asked to answer several questions, in particular about

the meaning of the word, the frequency of its use, possible synonyms and forecasts regarding the potential consolidation of the lexeme in the vocabulary of the language.

Anticipating the results of the analysis, it is worth making a reservation that residents of the southern counties of England — Hampshire, Surrey and West Sussex and the unitary administrative units of Brighton, Portsmouth and Southampton took part in the survey. This fact could have influenced the results of the survey, since, perhaps, in other parts and counties of the UK, the language trends are somewhat different.

In the twentieth century, most neologisms needed time to firmly establish themselves in the language of everyday communication. However, as one might assume, in the last decade, with the development of information technologies, social networks and other diverse and broad opportunities for communication, there has

been not only an intensification, acceleration of the creation process, but also, what is fundamentally important for us, the rapid spread of new words both in this language collective and around the world.

The results were somewhat unexpected, since a group of informants aged 25 to 45 years determined the meaning of only 36% of the words. However, when the words were already presented in context, the informants were able to understand the meaning of 90% of the words given. Informants in the age group of 20-25 years reported that they heard or met 50% of the words, recognizing them out of context. However, according to the respondents, only 15-20% of the new words that were selected for analysis are actively used. Basically, these are lexical units from the sphere of everyday life, new technologies and the political and economic block. In this regard, I would like to emphasize once again the specifics of the words we have chosen: most of the lexemes included in the survey were published in the lists of words of the year of the Oxford Dictionary, which are formed on the basis of a high frequency of use.

The attitude of informants to the vast majority of neologisms is quite negative. They were described as "stupid", "unnecessary" and unable to gain a foothold in the English language for a long time. This opinion was expressed by the majority of native speakers who took part in the survey, and, in particular, the entire age group from 25 to 45 years.

Such an opinion is not new, the extremely negative attitude of native speakers to new, unusual words has been noted repeatedly. *The Telegraph* claims that new words enter the language so quickly that they "pass by" an entire generation ('terms ... have entered the language so quickly that they have bypassed the entire generation') [The Telegraph URL: <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/newstopics/howaboutthat/11574196/new-forms-of-social-media-terms-which-parents-do-not-understand.html>].

Dan Clayton, analyzing the perception of language changes, quotes a number of media representatives who describe new words born in youth slang or coming from the American version of the English language as "decline", "degeneration", "destruction" of the English language ("decline, decay and collapse"), comparing them with Carolina gray squirrels, displacing indigenous species, thereby destroying the linguistic ecosystem (like the grey squirrel destined to drive out native species and ravage the linguistic ecosystem') [Clayton 2016: 86 87].

From a linguistic, research point of view, it should be noted that the emotional negative reaction of native speakers to new and often incomprehensible words and their potential does not reflect an objective linguistic picture.

Having analyzed the meaning of all the lexemes proposed for the survey, it can be stated with confidence that 90% of words appeared or developed new meanings to denote new realities that did not exist in the linguistic picture of the world before.

Words, which, at first glance, could be dispensed with and which could illustrate the redundancy of linguistic means of expression, make up approximately 10%. These are linguistic units that originated in youth

slang and entered the modern English language of some social and age groups. However, according to the exact observation of the famous Russian linguist I.B. Levontina, all these words appear because there are some lacunae in the language, that there are fragments of the linguistic picture of the world that are not described by language or described in a way that does not suit native speakers at this stage of development. So, for example, a new word may appear not to name a new object or a new reality, but for the purpose of implicitly expressing that new emotional component that is absent in other lexemes of the language that are close in meaning (stylistic factor of the emergence of neologisms, according to Gilber) [Levontina URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dfzCehnmHf8>].

The opinion of I.B. Levontina is in tune with the thoughts of the famous lexicographer John Algeo, who wrote: 'We use some new words because we take delight in them... They reflect changes in material and intellectual culture. And they show us something of the way human beings cope with problems and laugh at the absurdities of life'[Algeo 1991: 15].

Let's try to understand the reasons why many of the new words we have considered do not fall into active use among native speakers.

The above opinion of the Telegraph journalist regarding the large number of new words that entered the language so quickly that they "passed by a whole generation" is certainly one of the explanations for the results we have obtained. On the other hand, we should not forget about the concepts behind the new words themselves. Allan Metcalf suggested using a number of factors that determine the "viability", or, in the words of Paul Cook, the "success" of a new word [Cook 2010]. These are the frequency of use (frequency), the lack of evidence of meaning (unobtrusiveness), the breadth of distribution and diversity of use situations (diversity of users and situations), the potential ability of the word to form other forms and meanings (generation of other forms and meanings), as well as the duration of the existence of the concept itself, expressed by the data in a word (endurance of the concept to which the word refers). It seems that it is the factor of the variety of usage situations and, in some cases, the duration of the existence of the extra-linguistic concept itself that are key to understanding and explaining the results of the survey. Many neologisms are created to describe a specific situation (*moblivious, second screening, hangry, mansplain*, etc.), and their use is limited to the scope of this situation. The reasons for the creation of such neologisms have already been called: this is the desire to express one's thoughts or convey one's attitude to something using a minimum of linguistic means and spending less time. The short-term nature of some concepts that have received naming in the present period of time, or the apparent short duration and "frivolity" of the named concept (*normcore, sapiosexual, AFK*, etc.), can serve as another explanation of the reluctance of native speakers to use neologisms, acute rejection and rejection of many lexical units that have entered the English language and trying to find their place in it.

CONCLUSION

Summing up the reasoning about the reasons for the "success" or "failure" of certain neologisms of the English language, we note that language processes occur rapidly in comparison with past periods, within a few days as many new words appear as at other times appeared for several years. As I.B. Levontina aptly noted, the language in our time lives as if in accelerated shooting [Levontina URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dfzCehnmHf8>]. And if the language is a reflection of the life of the people, and the vocabulary is a kind of litmus test for social and cultural changes, then it can be assumed that new words, no matter how unusual and ridiculous they may seem to most of society at first, do not appear and become popular randomly. Their appearance is natural, as they bring with them new ideas and values.

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